

ON DISSYMMETRIES BETWEEN SOURCE TEXT AND TARGET TEXT: NEW PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The topic of the article covers the philosophy of polarity between source and target texts. It is well acknowledged that translation has to attempt to strike a balance between the interests of the original author and those of the translator to construct parallels between the two cultures, the histories that it brings together. Translating refers to a situation that lies midway between the ST and TT. The poles must meet in the middle at a certain point, which will always be that of the translator. We shall proceed to examine this relation in the purported $y = 1/x$ function, which is an excellent starting point from which to build an understanding of the investigated phenomenon. The evidence of research findings suggests that the relationship between ST and TP in the context of intermediary language is equivalent to the rational function $y = 1/x$, where y and X correspondingly stand for TT and ST. The concept of a vertical asymptote and a horizontal asymptote states that the translations, even the best ones, would never touch the X-axis, though they would get very close to it.

Keywords: Translation Studies, Source Text and Target Text, Asymmetry in Translation, Intercultural Communication, Colonial Discourse, Equivalence Theory, Philosophy of Language

It is well acknowledged that the conception of translation as an art (act of communication) supports the theory that translation is an interaction between two literatures and their respective cultures in which the source language continuously appears in opposition to the target language. It should be noted that ST-TT in literary hierarchy has never been pushed into the lumber room, and the study of the relationship plays an important role in oiling the wheels of intercultural communication. Source language goes with Target Language like the sun goes with the moon.

One problem in the field of translation studies is the relationship (linkage) between the text termed (worded) the original or the source and the translation of the original (target text).

Before embarking upon a detailed description, it is helpful to make some touches upon the problem of the relationship between the original or source text and the translation of this original from a historical perspective, i.e., looking at this with several views in mind.

There has been a polemic warfare between the source language and the target language. There was a time when the original was perceived as superior to the translation, which was relegated to the position of being merely a copy, albeit in another language. It is the concept of high-status original and today, assumptions about the powerful original are being questioned. "It arose as a result of the invention of printing and the spread of literacy linked to the emergence of the idea of an author as "owner of his or her text". For if a printer or author owned a text, what rights did the translator have? This discrepancy has been encoded into our thinking about the relationship between translation and so-called originals". (S. Bassnet and H. Trivedi, 1992, p. 2).

Tackling the relationship between SL-TL it is also important to remember that the myth of translation as something that diminished the greater original established itself in the period of colonies, when Europe was regarded as the great Original, the starting point, and the colonies were therefore copies, or "translations of

Europe, which they were supposed to duplicate. Moreover, being copies, translations were evaluated as less than originals" (S. Bassnet and H. Trivedi p.4).

Thus, the notion of the colony ranks the translation in a lesser (lower) position in the literary hierarchy and the translator as the servant of the source text. Translation has been at the heart of the colonial encounters and has been used in all kinds of ways to establish the superiority of some cultures over others. This is sometimes called *shameful history of translation*.

So how did colonies deal with that dilemma? How might they find a way to assert their own culture? How might they reject the copy or translation without at the same time rejecting everything that might be of value that came from Europe? They began to translate their own literature into European languages. However, today translation studies have challenged the longstanding assumption of translation as inferior to the original-assumption about the powerful original. Thus, present translation studies reassign (reappropriating) the notion of translation as inferior to the original, amplifying the thought that two language systems of evaluation and cultures vary within time and space as worded in Einstein's Theory of Relativity. In this understanding target text is really inferior to the source text; the main philosophy of subordination is embedded in culture, ideology, and history. Octavian Paz looks at this (stands a quite different point) from the opposite view, claiming that translation is the principal means we have of understanding the world we live in. Each text is unique, yet at the same time, it is the translation of another text. No text can be completely original because language itself, in its very essence, is already a translation- first from the nonverbal world and then inverbal, because each sign and each phrase is a translation of another sign, another phrase". (O. Paz, 1992, p. 154). It is fair to say that there are good seeds of argumentation in the assumption that "no text can be completely original because language itself in its essence is already a translation-from the nonverbal world". The author emphasizes the cognitive function of any text (any language)mirroring the worldview of the given nation on the one hand, and the worldview of the writer on the other hand;

in this context translation is designed in a broader sense. However, as we can see, this a radical view of translation, *labelling it not as a marginal but as a primary activity*. Tejaswini Niranjana goes even further , and suggests that translation both shapes and takes shape.

The dissymmetry tries between SL and TL exists today in the hierarchy of translation. But present interpretation has gained quite a different shape (understanding): "Translation is not a transposition of significance or signs. After the act of translation is over, the original work still remains in its original position. Translation is rather an attempted revitalization of the original in another verbal order and temporal space" (Ganish Devy p.186). In this asymmetrical context, it is the translator's labor to guarantee his/her faithful love to the foreign text as a thinker and a writer. "I had heard another's voice and was convinced that I could never say what he could as were as he did — at most it would have led to an unnecessary repetition" (Hans Erich Nos-sack p. 228).

The following statement by M. Gill and M.Guzman even sounds as a declaration "The translator is a part of contact between peoples , and since it is rare that two people have the same access to power , the translator is in a privileged position as mediator to make explicit the differences between cultures, expose injustices or contribute to diversity in the world" (M. Gill , M. Guzman pp.121-133).

These ways of thinking emphasize the necessity to take the translator toward the foreign text. Some insights into the mechanisms of these asymmetrical relations might be gained if we examine this relationship in the purported $y = \frac{1}{x}$ function. The primary task I intend to undertake here is the examination of the main contours of source text and target text relationship. The relation between ST and TT is equivalent to rational function $y = \frac{1}{x}$ where y and X - axes correspondingly stand for ST and TT. The figure 1 shows how the function looks.

Figure 1. The inverse relation between ST and TT, modeled by $y=1/x$

As we can see the graph line appears to be heading toward the edge of the diagram but is cut short of that.

Let us look at this function as it leaves the graph at the top and bottom. You should notice the function line approaches, but does not touch the Y-axis. If you graphed the function on a set of x, the function line would still not touch the y-axis, though it would get it very close. This type of behavior about the x-axis is called asymptotic, and in this case, the y-axis would be called a vertical asymptote of the function, and correspondingly x-axis would be called a horizontal asymptote of the function. As the Y-axis function line stretches out to the left or right, it gets closer and closer to the X-axis, but it never touches it. This is the concept of vertical and horizontal asymptotes. This is our concept of ST and TT. No matter how close, they never break the border between them.

Now, what we may ask is what this hyperbole does in an intermediate context. Does the relation between ST and TT acquire the same contour as in direct translation, or does it obtain another molding in a new time-space dimension? Target text in this new environment operates both as SL2 and TLI. Being distantly located from the main X-axis and closer related to a new lined X-axis, it operates like a mediator in the dialogue between these two poles, whose mission is to bring them closer on the one hand to ST-TT and on the other hand, to bring them as close as possible to the main y-x axis, of the function. Hence, TT/2/ passing in a new format gets a new shaping.

Thus, some scholars sought to relegate TT to a secondary status. Both the ST and TT descend from a common universal, rather than the latter deriving from the former.

The function $y = \frac{1}{x}$ is an excellent starting point from which to build an understanding of ST and TT. Such an approach enabled us to get valuable insights into the nature between SL and TL .

Conclusion

Translation has been at the heart of colonial encounter, and has been used in all kinds to perpetuate the superiority of some cultures over others. But now with increasing awareness of the unequal power of relations involved in the transfer of text across cultures, we are in a position to rethink both the history of translation and its contemporary practice.

As for the relation between ST and TT, it is equivalent to a rational function $y = \frac{1}{x}$.

The translation, even the best one, cannot be melted into the original, architecting a whole entity. In asymmetrical doctrine, they belong to different levels. Though they are opposed to each other, they are two sides of the same coin.

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